

Design of blue light visual damage detection system

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ABSTRACT

Blue light is an important environmental factor in people's daily lives. The main ways that people are exposed to blue light are daylight, mobile phones, computers, televisions, and so on. Blue light is the most dangerous visible light because too much exposure to it will increase the amount of toxins in the macular area of the eye, seriously threatening the health of our eyes. Therefore, it is necessary to design and make an affordable and convenient device that can help detect blue light and alert us when the damage reaches a specific threshold. This project uses a band-pass filter to filter out the visible light except blue light components. The collection circuit is made according to the working principle of photoresistor. An ESP8266 chip is used to convert the collected voltage into digital quantity that can be transmitted wirelessly, and then it is transmitted wirelessly to the mobile app. The app is developed for mobile devices to display cumulative exposure and raise an alert if above a threshold. Compared with professional blue light detection equipment, this system has the relative advantages of low price, small size, portability, and ease of secondary development, which provides a good solution for protecting our fundus safety.

Keywords

Blue light detection, Visual injury, Mobile APP, Wireless transmission

1 INTRODUCTION

Blue light is abundantly present in light sources such as computer displayers, fluorescent lamps, mobile phones, digital products, and LEDs. Blue light with a wavelength ranging from 400nm to 450nm has a short wavelength and high energy, making it the most sensitive and penetrating to the retina among visible light. It can directly penetrate the lens to reach the retina (Tosini, 2016), producing photochemical reactions that lead to irreversible damage such as the decay of retinal pigment epithelial cells and the loss of nutrients in light-sensitive cells (Martinsons 2015). It can also increase the toxin level in the macular region of the eye (Wu, 2018), posing a serious threat to our eye health (Sayan, 2019).

Blue light is everywhere in daily life, but the main sources of harmful blue light exposure are solar radiation and LED screens. In recent years, a large amount of nitrogen oxides generated by human activities have been emitted into the atmospheric environment and reacted with ozone in the stratosphere, consuming ozone and causing the concentration of the ozone layer to gradually decrease. The destruction of the ozone layer allows excessive solar radiation, including blue light, to reach the ground, further intensifying the harm to human vision (Roberts, 2021). In addition, most families watch LED TVs, as the main source of living room entertainment, before going to bed at night. Many people even turn off the lights when watching TV, coupled with factors such as screen flickering, leading to harmful blue light causing damage to the eyes, especially among children and adolescents who are undergoing critical developmental stages. The harm of TV blue light to the eyes should be given

sufficient attention (Takeshita 2013). Furthermore, computers have played an increasingly important role in human work. The average daily use time of computers by Shandong Provincial Government Agencies is 5.38 ± 2.85 hours (Wang, 2010). Due to prolonged exposure to LCD screens, the cumulative harm of blue light to the eyes can cause irreversible damage to vision.

The World Health Organization (WHO) and related vision associations have announced that one of the main reasons for the loss of vision and blindness affecting 30,000 people globally each year is blue light radiation (Meng, 2021). The harmful effects of blue light on human eyes are mainly manifested in pathological ocular hazards such as myopia, cataracts, and macular degeneration, as well as circadian rhythm disruptions (Lucas, 2014). The process of these injuries is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Blue light damage to the eye diagram

The harm caused by blue light does not necessarily mean that the presence of blue light will inevitably cause damage to the retina. The severity of the damage is the product of blue light intensity and exposure time (Bullough, 2017). Currently, we are exposed to the chronic harm of blue light, which is an "invisible killer," but we lack a convenient and fast alerting (Liu, 2014). The International Commission on Non-Ionizing Radiation Protection (ICNIRP) established guidelines for blue light radiation protection in 2013, proposing an exposure limit (EL) of $24 \text{ KJ} \cdot \text{m}^{-2}$ for the effective dose of blue light exposure to the retina.

Professional blue light detection equipment, such as blue light energy intensity detectors, has long been commercially available. However, they generally suffer from disadvantages such as high prices, bulky sizes, and difficulties in secondary development. Although they have high detection accuracy and comprehensive functionality, they are only suitable for use by professional institutions and cannot be widely promoted.

In this paper, a blue light detection and alarm system is proposed to address these limitations. This system collects visible light from an optical scene and filters it to obtain blue light. The resistance of a photosensitive resistor varies with the intensity of blue light, causing changes in the designed detection current. This current is then converted into a voltage signal through a circuit. A chip with wireless transmission capabilities collects the voltage signal, converts it from analog to digital, and establishes a calibration between the digital signal and the blue light intensity. The cumulative amount of blue light is measured in real time, and an alarm is triggered when the cumulative amount of blue light reaches a predefined threshold.

2 DISCUSSION

2.1 Scheme Design

This project has completed the first and second versions of the product respectively. The first version accomplished all the basic functions, while the second version improved on the first version, making it smaller and more convenient to use through wireless.

The first version of this project includes two parts: a detection unit and a display alarm unit, as shown in Figure 2. The detection unit mainly focuses on filter element selection and structure design, photoresistor detection principle research, and detection circuit design to realize blue light detection function; the display alarm unit mainly develops the cumulative metering module, display module, and alarm module in the program, realizing the real-time display and threshold alarm functions. The detection circuit and the display alarm unit rely on the relevant programs developed by Arduino IDE to realize the corresponding functions in Arduino UNO.

Figure 2. The first edition of research content

The Arduino UNO board is used as the development platform for the first version of the hardware circuit. Before building the hardware circuit, simulation verification is

performed on Proteus. Figure 3 shows the construction of the hardware circuit on Proteus.

Figure 3. Hardware circuit construction on Proteus

The probe is connected to the main body using a pluggable Dupont wire. The Arduino is powered by a battery. According to the size of the Arduino, acrylic plates were designed and cut, fixed with copper columns and screws. The battery and breadboard were glued to the bottom acrylic plate. At the same time, a position for the breadboard was reserved on the other side of the display. For future secondary development, the upper acrylic plate can be easily unscrewed with a screwdriver to facilitate the redesign and development on the breadboard. The finished product is shown in Figure 4, and the effect with power applied is shown in Figure 5.

Figure 4. Display of the work

Figure 5. Power-on effect of the work

After the completion of the first version, it was found that there were many cables, complex connections, large volume, and other deficiencies. Combined with the ESP8266 wireless transmission chip, we developed a new blue light detection and alarm system. Specifically, the second version of the project includes four parts: detection unit, data conversion unit, wireless transmission unit, and display alarm unit, as shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6. The second edition of research content

The second version of the product uses wireless transmission, and the mobile phone app alarm, significantly reducing the number of cables and also the volume, as shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7. Power-on effect of the second edition

2.2 Probe Module Design

2.2.1 Research on Blue Light Acquisition Principle

(1) Working principle of optical filter

The filter is an optical device used to select the desired radiation band, and filters out part of the light by absorbing some specific wavelengths. The vacuum coating machine deposits the film of different refractive indices to the optical substrate of the filter to achieve different optical effects, the use of light interference principle to obtain spectral transmission, a variety of wavelengths of mixed light through the filter, due to the different refractive index and interference effect, resulting in a specific wavelength of light has a very high transmittance and other wavelengths of light are reflected and absorbed.

(2) Working principle of photoresistor

Photoresistors are special resistors made of semiconductor materials such as cadmium sulfide or cadmium selenide, and their working principle is based on the internal photoelectric effect. The stronger the light, the lower the resistance value, with the increase of the light intensity, the resistance value decreases rapidly, the incident light intensity, the resistance decreases, the incident light is weak, the resistance increases. When it is illuminated by light, the electron-hole pair is excited in the semiconductor sheet (photosensitive layer), which participates in conduction and enhances the current in the circuit.

(3) Working principle of acquisition circuit

Since the Arduino analog input interface inputs a voltage of 0-5V, it is necessary to pass the current through the selected fixed resistance and collect the voltage value at

both ends of the resistance. According to Ohm's law, when the resistance of the photoresistor is changed under the influence of light intensity, the current changes under a fixed voltage, and the voltage at both ends of the fixed resistor in series in the circuit also changes, to achieve the purpose of obtaining light intensity by measuring voltage value.

2.2.2 Probe production

The probe is designed to be easy to measure and to simulate the structure of the human eye, so the final design is to separate the plug and pull the joint. According to the design requirements, in order to effectively simulate the blue light received by the human eye, a coated filter with a diameter of 10mm and a bandpass of 400-500nm was purchased. Use a knife to cut the pen holder of the discarded gel pen, and use the convex of the threaded connection part in the pen holder to fix the filter, as shown in Figure 8, so as to avoid the possible pollution of the filter caused by adhesive. The completed filter structure is shown in Figure 9. A 5mm space is reserved in the front of the filter (outside), mainly to simulate the human lens structure (lens diameter of 9-10mm, depth of 4-5mm), reduce the impact of side light on the photoresistor, make the detection result more real, and also play a role in protecting the lens. Place the photoresistor into the cylinder body of the light filter structure, mark a groove at the bottom of the cylinder with a knife, and use the friction between the pin of the photoresistor and the groove of the pen cylinder to fix it, and then wrap the probe with insulation tape at the bottom, as shown in Figure 10. In order to calibrate the photoresistor, a filter structure was made using the same method. A round hole as big as the lens was dug out on the protection cover of the illuminometer probe, and the filter structure was fixed on the protection cover of the illuminometer probe with 4030 glue, as shown in Figure 11.

Figure 8. Filter structure design

Figure 9. Filter structure

Figure 10. Fixation of filter structure and photoresistor

Figure 11. Filter structure and fixing of illuminometer

2.2.3 Design of Acquisition Circuit

Since the Arduino analog input interface inputs a voltage of 0-5V, the integer 0-1023 is returned. In order to improve the sensitivity of the system and facilitate measurement, the output value should be designed to be close to 0 at the lowest light intensity and 1023 at the highest light intensity according to the detection environment. In the actual measurement, it is found that the light intensity under the sun is much greater than that before the LCD, so the circuit is designed according to the first two modes of the LCD under the sun and the indoor LCD (LCD TV), and the DuPont thread is switched by plugging and unplugging. The illuminometer and photoresistor are used to obtain the maximum and minimum values of the measured values through multiple measurements. Considering the robustness of the system, the maximum light intensity display is 500-600, and the minimum light intensity display is 50-100.

The resistance range of the selected photoresistor under the experimental conditions of the LCD screen is about 0.8~1.4MΩ, after simple calculation and experiment, it is found that the photoresistor is connected with a 1 MΩ resistor, which can better meet the measurement needs of the daily computer screen. When tested in daylight or other strong light, the resistance of the photoresistor becomes smaller at this time, and a smaller resistance is required in series, so the two modes are designed separately. The collected photoresistor partial voltage signal is connected to the A0 analog pin of the Arduino board. Pin 10 is set as the status switch pin. Since there are two different display modes for the subsequent time display, use this pin to set the high and low level so that the program is displayed at different values.

2.2.4 Environmental noise modeling

Through research, it has been found that environmental noise can affect the entire acquisition circuit. It is also known that environmental noise is a type of Gaussian white noise that follows a normal distribution. Therefore, statistical knowledge is applied to construct a model of environmental impact using a large number of collected environmental noise signal samples.

$$\text{Let } \bar{X}_j = EX_j$$

$$\Delta x_{ij} = x_{ij} - \bar{X}_j \quad (i = 0, 1, \dots, m; j = 0, 1, \dots, n)$$

$$\Delta X_j \sim N(\mu_j, \sigma_j^2)$$

$$\Delta X \sim N(\mu, \sigma^2),$$

Define
$$\mu = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n \mu_j, \quad \sigma^2 = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n \sigma_j^2$$

In the formula, m represents the total number of samples collected in a certain scenario; n represents the total number of samples in a typical scenario; x_{ij} represents the i -th sample value collected in the j -th scenario; X_j represents the overall sample population collected in the j -th scenario; \bar{X}_j represents the mathematical expectation of the sample population in the j -th scenario; Δx_{ij} represents the noise of the i -th sample collected in the j -th scenario; ΔX_j represents the overall noise sample population in the j -th scenario; μ_j represents the mathematical expectation of the normal distribution followed by the noise in the j -th scenario; and σ_j^2 represents the variance of the normal distribution followed by the noise in the j -th scenario. Total noise sample population is denoted as ΔX , the mathematical expectation of the normal distribution followed by noise is denoted as μ , and the variance of the normal distribution followed by noise is denoted as σ^2 .

2.2.5 Identification method for detecting circuit output and temperature

Environmental temperature drift can directly affect the resistance of the photoresistor, which couples with the effect of blue light intensity on the photoresistor, directly affecting measurement accuracy. To address this, it is necessary to identify the relationship between temperature drift and circuit output. The least squares identification method is used to analyze and obtain the corresponding system response.

$$\Delta T = T_E - T_s$$

$$\Delta U = f(\Delta T, \Delta X)$$

In the formula, T_E represents the current ambient temperature, T_s represents the reference temperature, ΔT represents the difference between the current ambient temperature and the reference temperature; ΔU represents the deviation in voltage output of the detection circuit caused by temperature and noise; ΔX represents the overall noise sample population; and f represents the system response obtained through least squares identification.

2.3 Design of Data Conversion Module

2.3.1 Fitting Method for Blue Light Intensity and Digital Quantity

Using a lux meter to establish a basic mathematical model for blue light intensity refers to the noise-free conversion at the reference temperature.

$$P = g_1(D, T_s)$$

The above formula represents the basic mathematical model for blue light intensity established using a lux meter, which is a noise-free conversion at the reference temperature. In this model, P represents the converted light intensity output, D represents the digital signal output, T_s is the reference temperature, and g_1 is the conversion form using a power function fit.

After considering temperature drift and environmental noise

$$\Delta D = h(\Delta U)$$

$$P = g_2(D, \Delta D)$$

In the formula, ΔD represents the digital signal output under the deviation of the detection circuit voltage output caused by temperature drift and environmental noise; P represents the light intensity output after conversion; D represents the current digital signal; and g_2 is the power function fit form employed after considering influencing factors.

2.3.2 Data Type Conversion Method

Due to the use of serial communication, floating-point numbers such as blue light intensity and duration need to be converted into unsigned integer data for transmission according to the serial communication protocol. To achieve this, a union data type is set up in memory to share the same memory space for the floating-point number representing blue light intensity and the unsigned integer used for transmission.

At the wireless transmission chip end, the 64-bit double-precision data representing the blue light intensity is decomposed into eight 8-bit unsigned integer numbers, which are then sent according to the serial communication protocol. On the mobile phone side, after receiving the eight 8-bit unsigned integer numbers according to the serial communication protocol, they are converted back into 64-bit double-precision data to restore the blue light intensity. This process is repeated periodically through the use of a timer.

2.4 Wireless Transmission Module design

2.4.1 Application of Wireless Network Datagram Transmission Service

Traditional network transmission generally uses TCP and UDP protocols. Taking into account the real-time data collection and real-time alarm display requirements of the project, the project has chosen the connection-less UDP protocol and written corresponding call programs according to the protocol requirements.

2.4.2 Wireless Transmission Program Design

On the ESP8266 chip end, the WiFiUdp.h header file is included, and an instance of WiFiUDP named Udp is created. The baud rate is set to 115200. The ESP8266 is configured as an access point (WIFI_AP) using the WiFi.mode() function, and the WiFi access point's name (SSID) and password are set using the WiFi.softAP()

function. This allows for wireless transmission of the blue light intensity value through a timer-based loop. The program development interface is shown in Figure 12. This mode has a significant advantage: it facilitates easy connection for mobile phones through the creation of a hotspot, and local broadcasting allows for sharing among multiple devices. This enables multiple users to monitor using their mobile terminals.

```

my_udp_loop | Arduino 1.8.19
文件 编辑 项目 工具 帮助
my_udp_loop
#include <ESP8266WiFi.h>
#include <WiFiUDP.h>
#define STASSID "BlueLiaghtDetection"
#define STAPSK "12345678"
unsigned int localPort = 8888; // local port to listen on

// buffers for receiving and sending data
char packetBuffer[UDP_TX_PACKET_MAX_SIZE + 1]; // buffer to hold incoming packet,
char ReplyBuffer[] = "acknowledged\r\n"; // a string to send back
int intensity=0;

WiFiUDP Udp;

void setup() {
  Serial.begin(115200);
  WiFi.mode(WIFI_AP);
  WiFi.softAP(STASSID, STAPSK);
  IPAddress ip=WiFi.softAPIP();//获取ip地址
  Serial.println(ip);//打印出来ip地址
}
void loop() {
  IPAddress ip=WiFi.softAPIP();//获取ip地址
  Serial.println(ip);//打印出来ip地址

  Udp.beginPacket("192.168.4.255",8888);
  intensity=analogRead(A0);

  String s="";
  s=String(intensity);
  Udp.print(s);
  Serial.println(s);
}
    
```

Figure 12. Interface of IDE

The mobile phone program is developed using the Android Studio IDE. It constructs a transmission body by instantiating the UDPServer object and calls the socket.receive(packet) method to receive data. By instantiating the Timer object, a timer is set up to execute the receiving command periodically, enabling continuous retrieval of the blue light data sent by the ESP8266.

2.5 Alarm Module Design

2.5.1 Data Preprocessing Method

The connection-less UDP protocol is used in the second edition to realize real-time data collection. It cannot guarantee the correctness of each data transmission. Traditional data transmission typically relies on checksum verification, which means that if an error occurs, the entire batch of data must be discarded. Furthermore, in extreme cases, there may be several transmission errors while the checksum remains correct, posing a potential hazard to signal transmission and final detection accuracy. Therefore, a filtering processing algorithm is designed based on two criteria: threshold and slope. This algorithm judges each transmitted data value based on the upper and lower limits of the data type and its change slope. Only data exceeding the criterion

range is filtered out, fully utilizing the transmitted data and improving detection accuracy.

2.5.2 Display and Alarm Circuit Design

The LCD1602 industrial character LCD screen is used as the display module, which has the characteristics of low power consumption, small size, rich display content, ultra-thin and lightweight, and can display 2 lines and 16 columns of characters, the first line shows the real-time blue light intensity, the second line shows the cumulative running time of the system, that is, the blue light monitoring time.

In order to save ports, the LCD1602 and Arduino main board card are connected by four-wire method, and only Arduino digital pins 2, 3, 4 and 5 are used. The enable terminal E of LCD1602 is connected to Arduino digital pin 11, and the data and command selection terminal RS is connected to Arduino digital pin 12. By continuous comparison, the LCD1602 contrast adjustment terminal is grounded through a 1k Ω resistance. Power supply Select 5V voltage of Arduino board.

Programming the `lcd.setCursor(0, 0)` positions the cursor to the first line of the lcd1602 display, where the real-time blue light intensity is displayed using `lcd.print("Light: " + String(val))`. Due to the significantly higher light intensity outdoors compared to the LCD display, the alarm time is displayed in seconds. Indoors, however, the program is modified to display the time in minutes. For second-based display, `lcd.setCursor(0, 1)` positions the cursor to the second line of the lcd1602 display, and `lcd.print("Time: " + String(millis() / 1000))` shows the elapsed time in seconds since the program started running. For minute-based display, `lcd.setCursor(0, 1)` again positions the cursor to the second line, and `lcd.print("Time: " + String(millis() / 60000))` displays the elapsed time in minutes. The alarm is set to trigger when the cumulative blue light exposure reaches 80% of the effective damage dose threshold for retinal exposure, as recommended by Guo (2019). Calculations indicate that the alarm should be activated when the cumulative variable reaches 547,665. The green LED light is connected to the Arduino digital pin 13 through a 220 Ω resistor and serves as an indicator that the program is running properly. The red LED light is connected to Arduino digital pin 8 through a 220 Ω resistor as an alarm light output, and a small buzzer is connected to Arduino digital pin 9 through a 110 Ω resistor as an alarm voice alarm output to achieve sound and light alarm at the same time.

2.5.3 Display and Alarm APP Design

Instantiate a MediaPlayer object to implement the construction of the alarm sound, instantiate a Vibrator object to implement the construction of the alarm vibration, and instantiate a Button object to implement the construction of the alarm light. Utilize the `setOnClickListener()` method to pause and resume the monitoring process, satisfying the user's need to temporarily leave the monitoring environment. When the measured value is below the alarm threshold, cumulative calculations are performed. Instantiate an EditText object to create three display windows, showing the elapsed time, current blue light intensity, and cumulative light intensity, respectively. When the cumulative blue light exposure reaches 80% of the effective damage dose threshold, switch the alarm color to red by calling `setBackground-color(Color.RED)`, and simultaneously trigger the vibration and music playback programs to achieve various forms of alarms

such as sound, light, and vibration. The program development interface is shown in Figure 13.

Figure 13. Interface of the program design

2.6 Test Results and Analysis

2.6.1 Testing under Daylight

The specific testing procedures were as follows, conducted both in the morning and noon under outdoor conditions (sunny weather):

Step 1: Set up a bracket under outdoor daylight, horizontally fixing the probe at a height of 1.6m from the ground to simulate a person looking straight ahead in the sun.

Step 2: Connect the power supply and press the cumulative metering reset button to start measurements.

Step 3: Wait for the alarm signal to sound, and record the time and the current maximum blue light radiation intensity.

The test under daylight is shown in Figure 14.

Figure 14. The test under daylight

The result under daylight is shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Test result under daylight

Scene	Max Blue Light Intensity (μWcm^{-2})	Average Blue Light Intensity (μWcm^{-2})	Time Elapse (s)
Morning	3239	2700	711
Afternoon	10512	9320	206

2.6.2 Testing in Front of Computer LCD Display

Under indoor conditions, testing was conducted in both lighted and unlighted environments. The specific experimental procedures were as follows:

Step 1: Set up a bracket 40cm away from the center of the computer LCD screen, horizontally fixing the probe to face the center of the screen, simulating a person working in front of a computer.

Step 2: Connect the power supply and press the cumulative metering reset button to start measurements.

Step 3: Wait for the alarm signal to sound, and record the time and the current maximum blue light radiation intensity.

The test in front of LCD is shown in Figure 15.

Figure 15. The test in front of LCD

The result of viewing computer LCD is shown in Table 2.

Table 2. The result of viewing computer LCD

Scene	Max Blue Light Intensity (μWcm^{-2})	Average Blue Light Intensity (μWcm^{-2})	Time Elapse (s)
Lights on	124	116	275
Lights off	128	110	292

2.6.3 Testing of watching TV

Under indoor conditions, testing was conducted in two scenarios: with the lights on and with the lights off. The specific operational procedures were as follows:

Step 1: Set up a bracket 2 meters away from the center of the LCD TV screen, horizontally fixing the probe at a height of 1 meter from the ground, aiming it directly at the center of the TV screen. This simulates a person sitting on a sofa watching television.

Step 2: Connect the power supply and press the cumulative metering reset button to initiate measurements.

Step 3: Wait for the alarm signal to sound, and record the time and the current maximum blue light radiation intensity.

The test of is shown in Figure 16.

Figure 16. The test of watching TV

The result of watching TV is shown in Table 3.

Table 3. The result of watching TV

Scene	Max Blue Light Intensity (μWcm^{-2})	Average Blue Light Intensity (μWcm^{-2})	Time Elapse (s)
Lights on	136	127	251
Lights off	134	130	247

2.6.4 Analysis and Discussion

Through the testing conducted under the aforementioned three different application scenarios, it can be observed that the test results align with those obtained by professional equipment in literature, thus demonstrating the effectiveness of the project design. Additionally, the testing of the project has also reflected some misconceptions regarding blue light protection in our daily lives. It is necessary to wear sunglasses under strong sunlight, especially for teenagers whose eyes are still developing, and thus extra attention should be paid to protection against bright light.

3.CONCLUSION

A blue light visual damage detection system is designed. Although it has a single function and limited detection accuracy, it is convenient to carry and has the flexibility for secondary development through additional programming. Therefore, it is more suitable for ordinary people to use to help protect the health of their ocular fundus in daily life.

Although the product has achieved its basic functions, there are still some issues:

(1) The product requires manual calibration based on the noise and temperature drift of its environment. This calibration involves measuring certain data and programming specific parameters. Currently, the product cannot automatically calibrate itself in different environments.

(2) The research on the mechanism of photosensitive material detection is not yet deep enough, and we are still using readily available photoresistors.

To address these issues, the following explorations are planned:

(1) Programming will be further developed to enable automatic adjustment of environmental parameters. This will enable the product to automatically calibrate itself upon startup, making it more easily adopted in a wider range of scenarios.

(2) Under the guidance of our teacher, we will further investigate the characteristics of more photosensitive materials that are less affected by environmental factors, aiming to improve the accuracy of blue light detection.

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